

An Examination of Passenger Perceptions Towards Public Transit Express Buses

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Abstract: This study investigates passenger perceptions towards a public transit express bus service, aiming to understand satisfaction levels and identify areas for service improvement. The research surveyed 285 respondents using a convenient sampling method to collect data on their experiences with the express bus service. To analyse the data, the Mann–Whitney U test and Kruskal–Wallis test were employed to examine differences in passenger satisfaction with service quality across independent groups based on gender and age. These non-parametric tests were chosen due to the ordinal nature of the satisfaction data and to account for any non-normality in the distribution of responses. Additionally, an ordered logit model was utilized to investigate the relationship between passenger demographics (gender and age) and perceived service quality. This model helps to understand how these demographic factors influence overall satisfaction with the express bus service. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into passenger satisfaction levels and highlight areas for improvement in the service quality of public transit express buses. Understanding these perceptions is crucial for transit authorities to enhance their services, ensuring better customer satisfaction and more efficient long-distance transport operations. This research contributes to the broader field of public transportation studies by offering a focused analysis of a specific service provider, employing robust statistical methods to ensure the reliability and validity of the results.

Keywords: Public transportation, passenger satisfaction, express bus service, service quality, demographic analysis

JEL Classifications: L92, R41, R49, D12, C25

Introduction

The COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China, has had a significant impact on the public transit sector, leading to reduced travel demand and financial losses for bus operators (Saikat Hinge, 2023). The average profit margin of buses has decreased due to travel restrictions and negative perceptions from users. A city's transportation network is its cardiovascular system—a multifaceted structure that enables the continuous flow of people and goods through its arteries. Municipal authorities, city councils, urban planners, and transport-infrastructure owners and

operators around the world are well aware that its quality and efficiency are crucial for the economy and for the well-being of citizens. The development of the nation's economy depends significantly on the transportation system. The term "transport" refers to the movement of people and products between locations as well as the numerous methods used to carry out such movement. The transportation facilitates better access for both individuals and businesses to various regions. Transport promotes the global border range of social and economic integration. Many people have career options because of the transport system. Transport systems help people save time, effort and money. In the transport system, public transportation is imperative as it contributes to the development of sustainable and inclusive urban and rural mobility. Its relevance extends beyond mere movement of people, contributing significantly to social, economic, and environmental goals. Public transportation is essential for promoting accessible, sustainable, and affordable mobility, reducing traffic congestion, and lowering environmental impact. Research studies stress on the significant contribution of public transportation to socioeconomic activities and the long-term sustainability of communities globally (Salisu et al., 2023; Zhang, 2024). According to (Shaaban et al., 2021), a country's economy and population growth will benefit from an intelligent transportation system's contribution to a more managed and efficient road network. The transportation system consists of three fundamental elements: users, vehicles, and transportation infrastructure (Deb & Hinge, 2023). The majority of government financing for public transportation especially in developing countries like India goes toward buying new vehicles, yet this merely serves to increase the comfort and duration of trips. Given that the primary elements of service quality that people demand are equally significant for overall user satisfaction (Sinha et al., 2020). Within the public transportation system, express bus services play a key role by offering efficient, cost-effective, and comfortable long-distance travel with fewer stops, catering to commuters and intercity travelers. These services reduce reliance on private vehicles, alleviate road congestion, and provide a reliable alternative to trains or cars, especially in regions with limited transportation options. By enhancing regional connectivity and convenience, express buses contribute significantly to the overall efficiency and sustainability of public transport networks. Express bus services are essential for providing efficient and convenient transportation options for passengers, particularly in urban areas with high demand levels (Larrain et al., 2010). These services utilize strategies such as limited-stop routes, reserved bus lanes, smart card systems, queue jumper lanes, and high-capacity articulated buses to enhance their effectiveness (Alam et al., 2014). By offering faster travel times and reduced congestion, express buses cater to passengers seeking affordable and convenient long-distance travel options (Azman & Wea, 2021). Additionally, express bus services contribute to the overall efficiency of public transit systems by serving only a subset of stops along specific routes, benefiting both users and operators (Larrain et al., 2010). To ensure the success of express bus services, it is crucial to consider factors influencing customer intention to use these services. Research has indicated that providing valuable insights to bus carriers' managers and practical recommendations to policymakers can help enhance service quality and encourage more individuals to utilize express buses (Van et al., 2018). Optimizing bus scheduling, especially during peak hours, is

essential to improve operating efficiency and service levels, ultimately benefiting the public (Yuan et al., 2023). Implementing strategies such as the TOPSIS method for selecting the best bus transportation services allows public transport agencies to cater to diverse passenger needs and preferences while maximizing service quality (Seman et al., 2020). Efforts to enhance the reliability and regularity of bus services are vital for meeting passenger expectations and increasing ridership. Strategies like limited-stop bus services have been evaluated as effective means to provide competitive and attractive transit options (El-Geneidy & Surprenant-Legault, 2010). Furthermore, the implementation of various improvement strategies, along with the use of agent-based decision-support models, can aid in redesigning bus routes to better connect small cities and towns, thereby improving overall service quality and efficiency (Rasca, 2024). Understanding the impacts of different improvement strategies on transit service reliability allows agencies to address challenges and strive to offer more dependable services (Diab & El-Geneidy, 2013). In addition to service reliability, ensuring the safety of express bus services is paramount. Assessing safety from the perspective of bus operators is essential to identify potential risks and implement measures to mitigate them (Azman & Wea, 2021). Optimizing bus stop locations and distribution is crucial for enhancing walking access and improving feeder routes that connect residential areas to transport interchanges (Taplin & Sun, 2019). By considering factors such as population density and employment distribution, cities can develop efficient multi-modal transit services that cater to diverse travel needs (Huang & Liu, 2014). Benchmarking performance and sharing best practices among bus agencies can further enhance service quality and efficiency (Morse et al., 2020). By comparing performance metrics and adopting successful strategies, agencies can strive for continuous improvement and better meet passenger expectations. Additionally, ensuring fairness in local movements of tourists through just perceptions of bus services can lead to increased satisfaction and loyalty among visitors (Zoghbi-Manrique-de-Lara & Guerra-Báez, 2016). Fair and efficient bus services not only contribute to positive customer experiences but also support destination loyalty and tourism sustainability. Public transportation is experiencing significant changes driven by various trends and factors. (Shaheen & Cohen, 2018) identify five key trends influencing public transportation, including changing generational behavior towards suburbanization, new attitudes towards technology, shifting preferences for sharing and on-demand mobility, innovative travel alternatives, and the rise of flexible transportation options. These trends are reshaping the landscape of public transit systems in metropolitan areas. (Zhang, 2024) highlights the positive trajectory of urban public transportation sustainability, indicating ongoing improvements in the sector. (Koman, 2024) further supports this by noting a global trend towards integrating electromobility elements into public transport infrastructure, particularly since 2022. This shift towards electric mobility solutions aligns with the broader sustainability goals of many cities. In the realm of technology and information management (Hsu, 2012) discusses the application of just-in-time methods in public transportation systems, enabled by advancements in technologies like automatic vehicle location and real-time passenger information systems. These innovations are crucial for shaping seamless multimodal transit systems and improving overall efficiency.

The Kerala State Road Transport Corporation

The Kerala State Road Transport Corporation (KSRTC) is a key player in the state's transportation network, with a focus on enhancing efficiency and expanding services (Parthiban & Verghese, 2019). To meet increasing public demands, the corporation must continually optimize its network design and operations (Nair et al., 2023). Utilizing advanced data analysis techniques, such as time-series analysis for bus passenger demand modeling, provides valuable insights to enhance service quality and operational efficiency (Cyril et al., 2019). The corporation's performance is closely tied to the state's infrastructure and public services, with factors like literacy rates, healthcare accessibility, and transportation systems impacting outcomes such as mortality rates and service effectiveness (Suchithra et al., 2008). Especially in the context of public transportation during the COVID-19 pandemic, understanding passenger expectations and concerns is crucial for ensuring service quality and safety. The influence of external factors, like political systems, on Kerala's tourism sector underscores the interconnectedness of various industries and services within the state (Sandhya & Varghese, 2017). Moreover, the growth of rural markets in Kerala is bolstered by improved infrastructural facilities, including transportation networks, which in turn promote economic development and accessibility (Ns & Joseph, 2015; Xavier & Padmadas, 2000). Kerala's commitment to sustainable development extends to sectors like tourism, where transportation and communication networks play pivotal roles (Thimm, 2016). Kerala's distinctive characteristics, such as its high human development index and well-established healthcare delivery systems, contribute to the state's effective management of challenges like snakebite envenoming (Suchithra et al., 2008). Additionally, the state's emphasis on pre-hospital care systems and quality assurance in emergency medical services highlights the critical role of efficient transportation networks in saving lives and improving health outcomes (Brown et al., 2016; Patel et al., 2017). Studies on the driving behavior of public transport drivers and walkability to public transport emphasize the multifaceted approach necessary to ensure safe and accessible transportation services in urban areas (Sanjai, 2020; V., 2022). Infrastructure development, including transportation systems, significantly drives the economic growth of regions like Kerala and Gujarat, underscoring the importance of strategic planning and investment in this sector (Jha & Tandon, 2019). Factors influencing job satisfaction among healthcare workers, such as staff nurses in tertiary care hospitals, include the quality of transportation facilities that enable effective service delivery (Abraham, 2018). The experiences of public health nurses in providing maternal healthcare services to tribal women in Kerala underscore the critical role of accessible and reliable transportation in ensuring healthcare access for marginalized communities (Jose et al., 2013). A well-developed transport system is essential for all the citizens around the world. Like other areas, Transportation plays an important role in the economic development of the country. Mainly KSRTC buses are used by people according to their destination and convenience, in some routes only KSRTC buses provide services. People tend to choose their mode of transport by considering the amenity and security they get while traveling. The need of transportation systems are increasing day by day.

In olden days people used animals like, horses, donkeys etc. People also used tracks and water ways for the purpose of travelling, but in the changing world all importance were given to mechanical energy. People adopted various vehicles for travelling. KSRTC buses had created more employment opportunities among people. In India, people typically prefer to travel short-and medium-distances by bus. Due to their adaptability and accessibility to several villages and cities, buses have a significant advantage over other modes of transportation. It serves as a foundational infrastructure and public utility that caters to the general population's travel requirements for leisure, work, and educational endeavours. With quick and comfortable services available day and night, buses are now even a competitive alternative to trains on some long-distance routes. Kerala State Road Transport Corporation SWIFT (KSRTC SWIFT), also known as K-SWIFT, is an Indian transport company formed for operating long-distance buses of Kerala State Road Transport Corporation (KSRTC). The company was formed on 9 November 2021 with an aim to overcome the financial crisis faced by the KSRTC. K-SWIFT functions independently within the KSRTC and the company was dissolved and the assets merged with the KSRTC in 2021.

Passenger Perception in Public Transportation

The expectations and attitudes of passengers about public transportation services exhibit notable disparities Sharma & Pradhananga, (2021). Tyrinopoulos & Antoniou, (2014) stated that there was variability in the perception of passengers based on their gender, based on the study male are more satisfied than females on the services of public transportation. While males focused more on in-vehicle transit circumstances and the availability and caliber of transfer information, females focused more on waiting conditions, driver behavior, and punctuality. Cirillo et al., (2011) looked into how differently transport riders perceived the quality of their service and one of their main conclusions is that bus riders place a high value on reliability, and one-third of the sample is relatively willing to pay for on-time services. As per Deb & Hinge, (2023) Passengers perception about service attributes of public transportation was different pre-covid and post covid period, Users prioritise aspects including comfort, fairness, reliability & convenience, and safety in their pre-covid. In a study analyzing passenger satisfaction for both conventional bus transit and rail transit. The research utilized the AHP-EWM-FCE model to objectively quantify passengers' feelings about urban public transport services, revealing an overall passenger satisfaction rate of 91.2 percent (Zhang et al., 2020). While the importance of passenger satisfaction in influencing the utilization of public transportation was emphasized in a study. Which stated that understanding and meeting passenger requirements and preferences are crucial for enhancing public transport services and increasing passenger satisfaction levels Li et al., (2020). Research studies on the field have highlighted the perspective of service quality and its connection to customer satisfaction in the public transportation sector, highlighting the need for diverse perspectives in understanding and improving service quality. The significance of enhancing urban public transport service quality to meet customer expectations and improve overall service delivery advocate for satisfaction surveys as a reliable method to gauge user perceptions of service quality in public transport systems Ali et al., (2018); Belay, (2019); Echaniz et al., (2019). While, Zhao et al.,

(2023) identified critical factors such as travel speed, punctuality, price, and safety as key determinants of passenger satisfaction with public transport services. Factors influencing public transport passengers' satisfaction were explored in a research paper, which found that perceived value, perceived usefulness, and image significantly impact passenger satisfaction. However, perceived ease of use did not directly affect public transport passengers' satisfaction, indicating the complexity of factors influencing passenger experiences Sumaedi et al., (2016). Moreover, the provision of good information systems for public transport passengers, as suggested by Watkins et al., (2015) can enhance passengers' satisfaction and increase their interest in utilizing public transport services Setiabudi et al., (2015). Service quality factors are imperative in affecting passenger satisfaction with bus services. Improving service quality aspects is crucial for ensuring high levels of passenger satisfaction and enhancing the overall public transport experience Nguyen, (2023). Additionally, Imam, (2014) defined user satisfaction in public transport systems as the degree to which customers' expectations are met, emphasizing the importance of meeting and exceeding passenger expectations to enhance satisfaction levels. Further passenger comfort emerged as a significant factor influencing public transport usage and satisfaction. Kaitaro, (2024) emphasized the importance of passenger comfort in increasing public interest in using buses, underscoring the pivotal role of comfort in shaping passenger satisfaction and willingness to utilize public transport services. Moreover, Alborzi, (2021) revealed a significant correlation between passengers' sense of belonging and their satisfaction with urban road transport services, indicating the interconnectedness of emotional factors with passenger satisfaction.

Service Quality in Public Transit

To deliver better service quality, management of companies must first understand how customers view their offerings. The degree of service quality influences what consumers think of a service both before and after they use it Parasuraman et al., (1985); Parasuraman et al., (2005). Public transit service quality is a multifaceted concept that plays a crucial role in attracting and retaining passengers. Studies in this area emphasized that in public transport, service quality must be evaluated from the perspective of transit users, considering various factors such as demand, supply, and control conditions. Further highlighted the importance of high service quality in public transport to meet the diverse needs of customers and enhance passenger satisfaction. It echoes this sentiment by stressing that maintaining high service quality is essential for public transport to cater to a wide range of customer requirements and retain passengers Shen & Li, (2014); Anjulo, (2019); Nana et al., (2022). Wu et al., (2005) pointed the challenges faced by public transit agencies in enhancing service quality while ensuring adequate service coverage for passengers, this highlighted the delicate balance required to optimize service quality without compromising accessibility. Studies on public transit emphasized the pivotal role of service quality in influencing customer satisfaction, repurchase intention, and loyalty in the transportation industry, underscoring the significance of quality service provision in attracting passengers to public transport. Further explaining the dilemma faced by urban transit agencies in balancing service coverage, quality, affordability, and financial viability to meet passenger expectations while ensuring operational sustainability

Afedo et al., (2021); Verbich et al., (2017). Research studies stated that satisfaction in public transport as the degree to which customer expectations are met, highlighting the critical link between service quality and passenger satisfaction. Further delved into the attributes influencing service quality and passenger satisfaction in public transportation services, focusing on enhancing customer loyalty and satisfaction Kumar & Anand, (2013); Imam, (2014); Verma & Awasthi, (2020); Dewi & Guntara, (2022). Studies were carried out to assess the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in public bus services, aiming to enhance service quality to alleviate traffic congestion, and improve overall service delivery investigate customer expectations and their impact on satisfaction, loyalty, and environmental factors in public transport services, emphasizing the need to align service quality with customer expectations Kamaruddin et al., (2017); Ong, (2022); Dewi & Guntara, (2022). As per TCRP 165 service quality in public transport is defined as one that “reflects passengers’ perception of transit performance” (Transit Capacity and Quality of Service Manual - TCRP 165). A comprehensive list of forty-eight public transportation service quality attributes is provided in TCRP Report 47. These include characteristics pertaining to “service availability (like days and hours of service operation, time of access/egress and travel, etc), affordability (fare levels), comfort and convenience of passengers, information availability, staff behaviour and safety levels” (Morpace International Inc in association with Cambridge Systematics Inc). Quality aspects that are frequently thought to be significant in local public transportation have been highlighted by literature assessments. Four quality qualities are particularly important for consumer satisfaction: safety, punctuality, trip time, and frequency Dell’Olio et al., (2018) Hansson et al., (2019). Other frequently mentioned elements that have a significant impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty to public transit include costs, on-board comfort and cleanliness, and staff behavior. Van Lierop et al., (2018) Users start to value higher order attributes like cleanliness, safety, and customer service after basic attribute performances are reached and service quality improves. Users' expectations therefore increase as service quality increases, increasing their sensitivity to a wider range of variables Sinha et al., (2020). The public transportation information system is crucial to travelers' decision-making process, Since it is a tool to inform, instruct, and warn users of the potential choices they have when commuting Bachok & Razak, (2011). With regard to measuring service quality, SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al., (1988) is a pivotal and widely used study, which measured quality of physically delivered services by 5 dimensions namely, Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy. Further modifications to SERVQUAL model was done by various studies for assessing service quality based on the requirements of different industries. In a study the SERQUAL approach, which focused on bridging the gap between customer expectations and perceptions to enhance public transport services was adopted, which underscored the need for continuous evaluation and improvement of service quality in public transit to meet evolving customer demands Susnienė, (2012). A study on designing data collection methods for analyzing passenger satisfaction in public transport emphasized the key drivers of customer satisfaction, which included punctuality, travel speed, frequency, driver behavior, and vehicle cleanliness Blawal Hussain et.al, (2018). Filipovic et al., (2020) introduced the QUATTRO technique as a framework for assessing the quality of

service in mass passenger public transport modes, reflecting the evolving expectations and perceptions of service quality towards bus, auto and e-rickshaw. Verma & Awasthi, (2020) proposed the P-TRANSQUAL model for evaluating service quality in public land transport services, emphasizing the importance of a comprehensive approach to assessing and improving service quality in public. However, factors influencing passenger satisfaction in one region or service type may differ significantly from another due to cultural, geographical, or operational variations. By integrating service quality aspects from various studies, researchers can create a more tailored and comprehensive assessment that better reflects the specific needs, experiences, and expectations of the passengers.

After COVID, bus service attributes like cleanliness and vehicle condition became even more important to users. Heilig et al., (2015) in his study performed bibliometric analysis and provided insights into the field of public transportation from a meta perspective. In contrast to studies on local public transportation, their keyword analysis suggested that there are very few publications that focus only on regional public transportation. Urban planning, urban traffic, urban areas, urban development, and urban area are five of the 59 most popular terms. The keywords that are included have nothing to do with regional public transportation; none of the terms "regional," "rural," or "interurban" are present. Despite the growing emphasis on public transit systems as a sustainable transportation solution, there remains a gap in understanding the specific factors that influence passenger perceptions and satisfaction with express bus services. While general service improvements have been explored in various transit studies, there is limited research that specifically examines how passenger demographics, such as age and gender, impact their perception with quality of services. This lack of detailed understanding hinders the ability of transit authorities to effectively address the diverse needs of passengers and optimize service offerings. Therefore, this study seeks to address this gap by investigating the perceptions of passengers toward public transit express buses, with the aim of identifying key areas for service improvement based on demographic influences. Thus, this paper attempts to understand the perception of passengers towards KSRTC SWIFT Bus and also investigate how passenger gender and age influence the perception of the service.

Methodology

The study follows a cross-sectional survey design and the data were collected using a structured questionnaire from the passengers of KSRTC SWIFT services. The study employed a convenience sampling technique to collect data from passengers of KSRTC SWIFT express bus services. Convenience sampling was chosen due to its practicality and efficiency in reaching respondents who had recently used the service. The sampling frame included passengers from the KSRTC SWIFT Gajaraja Sleeper A/C Bus, Garuda A/C Seater Bus, Non-A/C Deluxe Bus, and Super-Fast Bus services. The study targeted Keralites who had used these services within the past month, ensuring that the data reflected recent and relevant travel experiences. The study focused only on distance journeys and did not consider the city circle services. Passenger information was gathered through a structured questionnaire administered to individuals who were either on board the KSRTC SWIFT buses or had completed their journey within the previous month. To reach passengers, the survey was distributed both in-

person and via online platforms. Passengers were invited to participate voluntarily. For in-person data collection, surveyors approached passengers either at bus terminals or on the bus, briefly explaining the purpose of the study and requesting their participation. For online distribution, passengers who had booked tickets through the KSRTC online portal were contacted via email or social media platforms and online questionnaire version was circulated among the respondents. A total of 327 responses were received, and 285 usable responses were considered for the study.

The questionnaire for the study was adapted from similar studies and the items were modified to fit the socio-cultural context of the study. The questionnaire contains two parts; participants' demographic details in the first part and 23 items to measure the service quality of SWIFT services in the second part. Given the increased interest in psychographic or lifestyle data among marketing professionals, demographic data is an essential and often critical component for segmentation and targeting. The goal of demographic data is to gain a deeper understanding of each respondent's unique background characteristics. Research studies will need to consider age, gender, and income in order to establish whether there is a meaningful relationship between consumer demographics and customer demand Hernández et al., (2011); Grazhdani & Merollari, (2015); Blawal Hussain et.al, (2018); Jasmine Tatoy et al., (2022). The service quality items were measured on a five-point Likert scale where, 1 = strongly dissatisfied to 5 = strongly satisfied Zhao et al., (2023). Though SERVQUAL, is the most significant study that contributed to the instrument's design for measuring aspects of service quality, the way different industries evaluate perceived service quality varies. Standardized models may not fully capture the context-specific factors that influence passenger perceptions in a particular region or service type. The operational features, demographic composition, and expectations of passengers can vary significantly across different settings, making it essential to develop a more tailored scale. By incorporating variables from various studies, this research aims to construct a comprehensive and contextually relevant framework that more accurately reflects the nuances of the service quality being studied. So, in this study the scale was developed by the researcher considering the special peculiarities of public transit express buses, and considering variables from the relevant literatures on service quality and public transportation. The major literatures considered for identifying variables were Parasuraman et al., (1988); Alborzi, (2021); Ibrahim et.al., (2021); Zhao et al., (2023); Kaitaro, (2024). The 27 items measuring service quality perception of passengers towards KSRTC-SWIFT bus services was initially identified.

Analysis and Results

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed in the study to identify the underlying structure of passenger perceptions regarding service quality. Given the multidimensional nature of service quality. EFA helped in reducing the number of observed variables by grouping them into a smaller set of latent factors that explain the correlations between these variables.

Further satisfaction data, which is ordinal in nature, were analyzed using two non-parametric tests—Mann–Whitney U and Kruskal–Wallis tests—to examine differences in satisfaction levels across demographic variables, specifically age and gender. Additionally, an ordered logit

model was applied to further investigate the relationship between passenger demographics and their perceived service quality. This model helped explore how factors such as gender and age influence overall satisfaction, enabling the study to provide deeper insights into the demographic factors that affect perceptions of service quality. These statistical methods were chosen to account for non-normal distributions in the data and ensure a robust analysis. IBM SPSS 25.0 was used to analyse the data.

Profile of respondents

The socio-demographic profile of respondents included their gender, age, education, occupation, monthly income, driving license and car ownership Ibrahim et.al., (2021).

Table 1 - Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	151	52.98
	Female	134	47.02
Age	Less than 25	26	09.12
	26-35	63	22.10
	36-45	94	32.93
	46-55	83	29.12
	Above 55	19	06.67
Education	1-7	18	06.32
	8-10	29	10.18
	Higher Secondary	45	15.79
	UG / PG	128	44.91
	Others	65	22.81
Occupation	Government /Public Sector	59	20.70
	Private Sector	132	46.32
	Self Employed	38	13.33
	Unemployed	19	6.67
	Student	37	12.98
Monthly Income (In INR)	Less than 10,000	56	19.65
	10,001 – 15,000	81	28.42
	15,001 – 20,000	89	31.23
	20,001 – 25,000	37	12.98
	Above 25,000	22	07.72
Driving License	Yes	234	81.11
	No	51	17.89
Car Ownership	0	102	35.79
	1	161	56.49
	2	18	06.32
	More than 2	4	01.40

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis using varimax rotation was performed to understand the factor structure of 27 items used to measure the service quality perception of passengers towards KSRTC-SWIFT bus services.

Table 2: Exploratory Factor Analysis				
Factor / Items	<i>EFA (PCA Using Varimax Rotation)</i>			
	Factor Loading	Eigenvalue	Explained Variance	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>KMO = 0.826, $\chi^2 = 16011.216, p < 0.000$</i>				
Comfort (CM)				
CM1	0.722	6.337	35.27	0.845
CM2	0.820			
CM3	0.675			
CM4	0.773			
CM5	0.755			
Staff Service (STS)				
STS1	0.770	3.419	12.83	0.812
STS2	0.800			
STS3	0.730			
Speediness (SP)				
SP1	0.627	1.821	8.54	0.804
SP2	0.732			
SP3	0.852			
SP4	0.664			
Facilities (FC)				
FC1	0.671	1.797	7.83	0.818
FC2	0.737			
FC3	0.897			
FC4	0.605			
FC5	0.641			
FC6	0.589			
Safety (SF)				
SF1	0.652	1.196	5.91	0.794
SF2	0.506			
SF3	0.666			
SF4	0.721			
SF5	0.614			
Ticketing Service (TCS)				
TCS1	0.918	1.097	3.64	0.876
TCS2	0.879			
Provision of Information (PVI)				
PVI1	0.798	1.017	2.22	0.905
PVI2	0.819			

The results of Exploratory factor analysis indicated that seven factors had eigenvalues greater than 1, namely comfort (CM) - 5 items, staff service (STS) -3 items, speediness (SP) - 4 items, facilities (FC)- 6 items, safety (SF)- 5 items, ticketing service (TCS)- 2 items, and provision of information (PVI)- 2 items, and these factors explained the 76.24 per cent of the total variance. The results of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO = 0.826) and Bartlett’s test of sphericity ($\chi^2 = 1611.216, p < 0.000$) were found to be significant indicating that there is a high sampling adequacy and the matrix has adequate common variance. The factor loadings of all the items were above 0.50, ranging between 0.506 and 0.918 and therefore all the items were retained. The Cronbach’s alpha values of the factors are above the threshold of 0.70 indicating greater reliability of the scales used in the study.

Effect of Gender and Age on passenger satisfaction with Service Quality

Morton et al., (2016) highlighted that it is essential to comprehend the different opinions toward the quality of public transportation services among the various socio demographic sectors. Studies reveal that the quality of service varied depending on the age and gender of the passenger, every age and gender group has a different opinion about the caliber of the services Bellizzi, (2020); Bose, (2020); De Oña, (2020); Obsie, (2020)

Ibrahim et.al., (2021) stated that passengers’ gender and age influence their perception of service quality. Thus, the following hypothesis were formulated:

H1: Gender has an influence on passenger perception of service quality dimensions of KSRTC Swift.

H2: Age has an influence on passenger perception of services quality dimensions of KSRTC Swift.

Table 3: Effect of gender and age on passenger satisfaction with service quality

Factor	M	Gender		Age	
		Z ^a	P-Value	(χ^2) ^b	P- Value
CM	4.0	-3.236	≤ 0.001**	35.315	≤ 0.001**
STS	4.0	-2.868	≤ 0.005*	22.877	≤ 0.001**
SP	3.5	-2.573	0.010 ^{n.s.}	24.145	≤ 0.001**
FC	3.5	-3.362	≤ 0.001**	31.758	≤ 0.001**
SF	4.0	-3.853	≤ 0.001**	2.596	0.850 ^{n.s.}
TCS	4.0	-1.433	0.110 ^{n.s.}	1.965	0.810 ^{n.s.}
PVI	2.5	-1.330	0.105 ^{n.s.}	20.837	≤ 0.001**

Note: A = Z score for Mann–Whitney U test, b = Chi-square score for Kruskal–Wallis Test, M = Median.
 ** significant at 1 % level
 *Significant at 5% level
 n.s. Not Significant

The study employed the Mann–Whitney U test and Kruskal–Wallis test (Table 3) respectively to compare the effect of gender and age on the seven dimensions of service quality since the data failed to follow a normal distribution. The median of the dimensions ranges from 2.5 to 4.0. Provision of information has the lowest median (M=2.5), while Comfort (M=4.0), Staff Services (M=4.0), Safety (M=4.0) Ticketing Services (M=4.00) have the highest median. The median for Speediness and Facilities was 3.5. The results of the Mann - Whitney U test show that there is a statistically significant difference between male and female passengers for comfort ($p \leq 0.001$), staff services ($p \leq 0.005$), facilities ($p \leq 0.001$), safety ($p \leq 0.001$), while there is no significant difference among gender groups for Speediness ($p = 0.010$), Ticketing services ($p = 0.110$) and Provision of information ($P=0.105$) at 5 per cent level of significance. The Kruskal - Wallis further indicated a significant variation in comfort ($p \leq 0.001$), Staff Services (≤ 0.00), Speediness ($p \leq 0.001$), Facilities ($p \leq 0.001$), and Provision for Information ($p \leq 0.001$) among different age groups.

Table 4: Results for the ordered logit models (Model 1 to Model 5)

Table 4: Results for the ordered logit models (Model 1 to Model 5)										
	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4		Model 5	
	General Model		Male		Female		18-35 Years Old		≥ 36 Years Old	
	β	S.E.	β	S.E.	β	S.E.	β	S.E.	B	S.E.
CM	0.230	0.069	ns.	ns.	0.156	0.058	0.185	0.045	ns.	ns.
STS	0.114	0.051	ns.	ns.	0.071	0.037	ns.	ns.	0.136	0.085
SP	ns.	ns.	0.159	0.054	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	0.124	0.061
FC	0.070	0.041	0.228	0.079	0.132	0.068	0.118	0.040	0.228	0.071
SF	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	0.136	0.077	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.
TCS	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.	ns.
PVI	0.180	0.047	ns.	ns.	0.228	0.071	0.040	0.046	0.097	0.048
N	285		151		134		89		196	
Nagelkerke R ²	0.638		0.654		0.602		0.623		0.608	

The study further performed five ordered logit models (Table 4) to determine the service quality dimensions contributing to the overall satisfaction of KSRTC SWIFT bus services. The dependent variable was overall service quality and the independent variables were the seven factors of service quality initially identified. Model 1 was developed for the entire sample, model 2 for males, model 3 for females, model 4 for those aged from 18 to 35 and the final model for those aged above 35. Following the previous research, the study considered age and gender only for segmentation purposes to perform in-depth analysis and to eliminate the heterogeneity of the data. The study follows a ten per cent level of significance to interpret the results.

The results of the general model (model 1) show that comfort($\beta=0.230$), staff service ($\beta=0.114$), provision of information ($\beta=0.180$) and facilities ($\beta=0.070$) have significant effects on passengers’ level of satisfaction with KSRTC – SWIFT Services. Comfort holds the highest

estimated coefficient following the provision of information in this model. The results of model 2 for males indicated that they prefer Speediness ($\beta=0.159$), facilities ($\beta=0.228$) and the model 3 for females show that they consider Comfort ($\beta=0.156$), Staff Service ($\beta=0.071$), facilities ($\beta=0.132$), safety ($\beta=0.136$), provision of information ($\beta=0.228$). Male passengers consider facilities as the critical factor following speediness while female passengers prefer the provision of information following comfort as the critical factor influencing their overall satisfaction with service quality. Models 4 and 5 for age categories also show significant differences among the groups. Passengers aged from 18 to 35 consider Comfort ($\beta=0.185$) as the critical factor following facilities ($\beta=0.118$) and provision of information ($\beta=0.040$), while passengers aged above 36 preferred facilities ($\beta=0.228$) as the key factor following safety ($\beta=0.156$), Staff Service ($\beta=0.136$), Speediness ($\beta=0.124$) and provision of information ($\beta=0.097$). The Nagelkerke R2 coefficient of all models ranges from 0.602 to 0.654 indicating a strong relationship between the variables.

Discussion

The aim of the research was to identify the perception of passengers towards KSRTC SWIFT Bus and to analyse how the demographic variables such as Age & Gender influences the perception of passengers. Passengers of KSRTC SWIFT Gajaraja Sleeper A/C Bus, Garuda A/C Seater Bus, Non-A/C Deluxe Bus and Super-Fast Passengers constitute the population of the study. The findings of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing passengers' perceptions of service quality on KSRTC-SWIFT bus services, highlighting the relevance of seven distinct dimensions: comfort, staff service, speediness, facilities, safety, ticketing service, and provision of information. These dimensions together explain 76.24 percent of the total variance in service quality perception, demonstrating a robust factor structure. The high Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.826 and the significance of Bartlett's test confirm the adequacy of the sample and the appropriateness of factor analysis, indicating that the dataset is suitable for extracting meaningful latent factors. The dimensions identified align with service quality models from other public transportation studies, such as (Parasuraman et al., (1988) SERVQUAL model and subsequent adaptations within transport services. Similar studies have also emphasized comfort, staff behavior, and safety as critical drivers of passenger satisfaction Chou et al., (2011); Redman et al., (2013). The findings further substantiate that these dimensions are essential components in shaping positive service perceptions in the context of long-distance bus services, a result that resonates with the literature on passenger satisfaction in intercity transport Eboli & Mazzulla, (2011).

However, this study expands on the existing literature by focusing on the express bus services in the specific context of KSRTC-SWIFT, revealing nuanced insights into gender and age-based differences in service expectations. The Mann-Whitney U test showed that significant differences exist between male and female passengers in relation to comfort, staff service, facilities, and safety, while no significant differences were observed for speediness, ticketing services, or the provision of information. This finding suggests that women place a greater emphasis on comfort, staff interaction, and safety, consistent with studies like Beirão and

Sarsfield Cabral, (2007), which report that women tend to prioritize these factors more due to safety concerns in public transport. For male passengers, the importance of speediness and facilities highlights a more utilitarian view of public transport, focusing on efficiency and service amenities. Age-based differences further illustrate the heterogeneous nature of passenger expectations. Younger passengers 18–35 years prioritize comfort, facilities, and the provision of information, possibly reflecting their need for convenience and up-to-date travel information, as supported Tyrinopoulos and Antoniou, (2008), who found that younger users of public transport are more likely to value technological services and amenities. In contrast, passengers aged above 35 prioritize facilities and safety, indicating that older passengers may be more concerned with physical security and the availability of reliable infrastructure. The Kruskal-Wallis test findings echo previous research that highlights age-related differences in public transportation preferences Friman & Felleson, (2009). In terms of age, the younger group 18–35 years places significant emphasis on comfort and provision of information, which may reflect their reliance on clear communication about routes and schedules and the growing demand for technology-enabled services, such as real-time updates. Meanwhile, older passengers above 35 years prioritize facilities and safety, which underscores the need for reliable physical infrastructure and a secure travel environment, findings corroborated by studies on older passengers' transportation preferences Alsnih & Hensher, (2003).

The ordered logit models provide further depth by indicating that comfort, staff service, facilities, and the provision of information significantly contribute to overall passenger satisfaction. Comfort emerges as the most influential factor across both gender and age groups, reaffirming its central role in enhancing the travel experience. Similar results have been noted in studies on long-distance and intercity bus services, where comfort is consistently highlighted as a primary determinant of satisfaction Eboli & Mazzulla, (2007). The models also show that while men prioritize speediness and facilities, women tend to value comfort, staff service, safety, and the provision of information more. These findings align with the results of Hensher et al., (2003), who found that women tend to have higher expectations of interpersonal service quality and information clarity in public transportation services. The Nagelkerke R^2 values, ranging between 0.602 and 0.654, indicate a strong predictive ability of the models, suggesting that the selected service quality dimensions significantly influence overall passenger satisfaction. These findings underscore the importance of addressing the diverse expectations of passengers across gender and age groups, ensuring that service improvements are tailored to the specific needs of each demographic segment.

Thus, results of this study contribute to the growing body of literature on public transportation service quality by offering a detailed examination of passengers' perceptions of KSRTC-SWIFT express bus services. The identification of key factors such as comfort, staff service, and the provision of information provides actionable insights for transport authorities, enabling them to target areas for improvement. Additionally, the gender- and age-specific differences in service expectations highlight the need for a more segmented approach to enhancing service quality, ensuring that the diverse needs of passengers are effectively addressed. This study's

findings align with, and build upon, previous research, reinforcing the significance of tailored service strategies in public transportation systems.

KSRTC SWIFT must consider steps to make the experience of the journey more comfortable to the passengers in terms of service and travel. Passengers expect more speed in long distance travel, so that they can reach destinations promptly. The Government should amend the laws accordingly to increase the speed limit especially on national highways. More avenues for information should be provided regarding the time schedule and fare of KSRTC SWIFT services. The company should consider listing the services private online bus booking platforms.

Summary and conclusion

The Govt of Kerala incorporated KSRTC SWIFT LIMITED. The Indian Companies Act has this company registered. In accordance with a contract with KSRTC, this company seeks to give the KSRTC the operational, administrative, technological, and infrastructure support it needs to run its long-distance services effectively. This study aligns with the existing body of literature that emphasizes the significance of understanding passenger perceptions in shaping the success of public transit systems. By investigating the factors influencing passenger satisfaction and dissatisfaction with KSRTC's SWIFT buses, this research contributes valuable insights to the broader discourse on public transportation optimization and service enhancement. Furthermore, in the context of the growing urbanization trend and the increasing demand for efficient transit options, insights into passenger perceptions become essential for transit agencies globally. Learning from the experiences and preferences of passengers towards the SWIFT buses can offer practical recommendations for KSRTC and contribute to the overall advancement of urban mobility solutions. As per the study female passengers prioritise information supply over comfort as the crucial component impacting their overall satisfaction with service quality, male passengers rank amenities as the most important feature, followed by speed. Different age groups have varying preferences when it comes to the important aspects of passenger perception. KSRTC SWIFT needs to think about how to improve the quality of service and travel for people on the trip. Long-distance travellers anticipate greater speed in order to arrive at their destinations on time. The government ought to revise the legislation to raise the speed limit, particularly on national routes. There should be more ways to get information about the hours and cost of KSRTC SWIFT services. The business ought to think about putting its services on private online bus reservation platforms. Building on the findings and addressing the limitations of this study, several areas for future research can be identified. Longitudinal studies could be conducted to track changes in passenger perceptions and satisfaction over time, helping to identify trends and the long-term impact of any service improvements or policy changes. Comparative studies across different regions or countries could provide a broader perspective on how cultural, economic, and infrastructural differences affect passenger satisfaction with public transit services. This could also include comparisons between urban and rural public transit systems. Further research could investigate the impact of emerging technologies, such as real-time tracking, mobile ticketing, and smart transportation

systems, on passenger satisfaction and service quality. Assessing how these innovations are adopted and perceived by passengers can inform future transit improvements. While this study considered gender and age, future research could delve deeper into other demographic variables, such as income levels, education, and occupation. Understanding how these factors influence passenger perceptions can help tailor services to meet diverse needs. Evaluating the effectiveness of specific service quality improvement interventions, such as enhancements in comfort, safety, and information provision, could provide actionable recommendations for transit authorities. Implementing and assessing targeted interventions could help optimize public transit services and improve overall passenger satisfaction. Finally, incorporating qualitative methods, such as interviews and focus groups, could provide deeper insights into passenger experiences and perceptions, complementing the quantitative findings and offering a more nuanced understanding of public transit service quality.

Appendix A

Factor/Item	Abbrev.
Comfort	CM
Level of lighting at the station	CM1
Appropriate ventilation and temperature at the station	CM2
Cleanliness at the station	CM3
Appropriate ventilation and temperature in the bus	CM4
Cleanliness in the bus	CM5
Staff Service	STS
Satisfaction with staff's attitude	
Satisfaction with travel experience	
Impact of employees' attitude on repeat travel behavior	
Speediness	SP
Punctuality of bus arrival	SP1
Acceptable bus dwell time	SP 2
Acceptable departure interval	SP3
Acceptable service time	SP4
Facilities	FC
Suitable location for vending machines	FC1
Suitable location for bus station waiting seats	FC2
Comfortable waiting seats	FC3
Comfortable armrest and ring setting in the bus	FC4
Mobile signal strength at the stations	FC5
Mobile signal strength on the bus	FC6
Safety	SF
Safety at the station	SF1
Safety in the bus	SF2
Safety during the travel	SF3
Behaviour of other passengers	SF4

Advance door closing announcement	SF5
Ticketing Service	TCS
Perception of the reasonableness of the price charged	
Perception of the affordability of the price charged	TCS 1
Satisfaction with the convenience fee charged	TCS 2
Provision Of Information	PVI
Accessibility of real-time updates on delays or route changes for KSRTC SWIFT buses	PVI 1
Satisfaction with real-time information on seat availability for KSRTC SWIFT buses	PVI 2

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